

MEMORANDUM
OPPOSITION TO THE "PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS
AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL, 2021"

Submitted to:

The Clerk to the Committee
The Committee on Constitutional, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs
Office of Parliament, Osu - Accra, Ghana

Submitted by:

A [REDACTED] D [REDACTED]
a [REDACTED]@gmail.com
30/09/2021

With respect to your advertisement in the Daily Guide Newspaper on 9th September 2021, I wish to submit this memorandum in opposition to the "Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021."

My name is A [REDACTED] D [REDACTED], I am a Ghanaian artist. As a citizen of this nation, I wish to register my opposition to the passing of this Bill for the reasons outlined below.

1. The Bill, if passed into law, will empower both the oppression of LGBTQIA+ people, **and** people wrongly perceived to be LGBTQIA+. It will result in malicious targeting of individuals who do not fit neatly into narrowly defined gender roles. The simple act of two friends holding hands could lead to oppression and persecution, and such fears and suspicions deriving from this could eliminate a wonderful part of the warmth and conviviality of friendship in Ghanaian cultures.
2. It is not the state's business to attempt to control the sexual activities of consenting adults. I request that our Parliament of representatives desists from passing this Bill with the intent to control the sexual activities of consenting adults.
3. Ghana does not have a state religion and consists of multiple cultures. Thus, the religious and cultural reasons referenced as driving the Bill in the introduction to the Bill do not represent all Ghanaians, including myself. I strongly reject any attempts to use the laws of Ghana as a tool to oppress my fellow Ghanaians who have done

nothing wrong and have not harmed anyone.

4. Furthermore, the human rights implications of this will draw negative attention to Ghana and destroy its reputation in the world as a welcoming and friendly country where people live in harmony despite their differences. The bill will cause many Ghanaians, especially in the creative industries to seek refuge abroad. Ghana will be perceived as being controlled and manipulated by churches overseas. Though I am not part of the communities being targeted, I support an adult individual's rights to live their private lives in peace. I already know of friends overseas who will no longer visit Ghana, if this bill is passed, out of principle and in support of their friends.

Thank you kindly for your consideration.

Best Regards,

A [redacted] D [redacted]